

Generative Adversarial Networks, Zero Sum Games, “Narcissistic Abuse”, Multi-Person Coping Mechanisms, Angels and “Demons”

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Generative Adversarial Networks

A Generative Adversarial Network is a strategy that consists of two neural networks, a generator network which creates data and a discriminator network (Google Developer GAN Course). The generator learns to generate believable fake data through being judged by the discriminator when it returns its opinion on whether or not the data it received was fake. The discriminator is penalized and learns when it either misclassifies real data as fake, or fake data as real. Eventually if the generator succeeds perfectly, then the discriminator will have a perfect 50% accuracy and it will not be able to distinguish real data from fake data. Essentially the generator “fakes it till it makes it” and the generator “keeps it real”. This generative adversarial network pattern is also referenced as a “Zero Sum Game” or a situation where “one persons gain is another’s loss”. This is because the both the gain of the discriminator and generator are dependent on the other losing.

Credit Google

As training progresses, the generator gets closer to producing output that can fool the discriminator:

Finally, if generator training goes well, the discriminator gets worse at telling the difference between real and fake. It starts to classify fake data as real, and its accuracy decreases.

Credit Google

Generative adversarial networks are unsupervised learning algorithms. This means that we do not need to have labelings or understandings of our data for us to gain information from our experiences. The information is instead gained through the adversarial process between the discriminator and the generator.

Narcissistic Personality Disorder

Individuals with Narcissistic Personality Disorder often overestimate their capabilities or hold themselves to unreasonably high standards (Cleveland Clinic). They also tend to brag or over-exaggerate about their achievements. They have frequent fantasies about having or deserving things like success and power, and they believe in superiority. However they feel a need for admiration from others to help support their confidence in this “false self”. People with Narcissistic Personality Disorder also tend to view the world in zero-sum terms.

Narcissistic Abuse Generative Adversarial Cope

Narcissistic abuse is a poorly defined term that often involves the individual with “Narcissistic Personality Disorder” gaslighting an individual for the reason of receiving validation that their false self is real and trying to hide the “false self” by any means necessary. This is almost identical to the generator wanting to receive positive response from the discriminator, while not wanting to be found out when generating fake data. This relationship between the individual with NPD and the “victim” is often a form of co-dependency, which generators and discriminators in GAN’s are quite literally co-dependent. It is also completely reasonable that the end goal would be something that is significantly superior to whatever is currently going on, because the discriminator then would move towards a solution that is to a significantly higher standard than what is currently present because they are gaining information by arguing with the generator (Individual with NPD). We want things to get better instead of worse for obvious reasons so the “Generator” individual is grandiose in their actions. This would also make sense because the development of Narcissistic Personality Disorder is generally triggered by trauma and poor life conditions something of which an unknown solution is likely needed. (Cleveland Clinic). To be on the other side of the “abuse” causes feelings of being unsure of oneself, significant trust issues, and often involves some form of attachment as well. These are both qualities of the discriminator. This re-definition is necessary for understanding and the removal of stigma.

Angels and “Demons”

It is said in the Bible that “demons” will possess people and they will try to mislead you into sin which could potentially be interpreted as making errors. I cannot prove that sin generally tends to lead to mistakes from a scientific standpoint, but I could imagine that pride, arrogance, anger, and self righteousness were probably at the forefront of a majority of them. It is said in the Bible that angels partake in spiritual warfare against the demons, however this evil in the end never wins. It is quite possible that these “demonic possessions” were in fact a compulsive coping mechanism, that caused them to mislead people around them from “god” or the knowledge we have in the stories we have learned. The most important thing is the separation of the “demon” and the individual who is “possessed”. This allowed these people to not have to bear

morale responsibility for things done while coping, such as dishonesty. Our current model of this absolutely demonizes these people, and it is about time we got back to a model that didn't.

Bibliography

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